

STUDIES ON SULPHONAMIDES AND ANALOGOUS COMPOUNDS. PART II.

By J. SIKDAR

A number of *p*-amino- and *p*-aminomethylbenzene sulphone derivatives has been prepared.

The observation of Klarer (*Klin. Wochsch.*, 1941, 20, 1250) that *p*-aminomethylbenzene sulphonamide is effective against anaerobic clostridia associated with war-wound infections, has opened up a new field for chemotherapy in bacterial infections. Unlike the common sulphonamide derivatives it is not affected by the presence of *p*-aminobenzoic acid (*cf.* Schreus, *Klin. Wochsch.*, 1942, 21, 671; Basu, Sen and Sikdar, *Science & Culture*, 1944-45, 10, 262). These observations and the recent findings (Bambas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 668, 671) that certain sulphones exert a chemotherapeutic action against pulmonary tuberculosis in animals, stimulated an interest in the search for some simple sulphones of the types (I) and (II), mainly with a view to studying the differences in their physiological and pharmacological actions against various aerobic as well as anaerobic organisms in presence of *p*-aminobenzoic acid.

The work is in progress, but as a paper on polymethylene-bis-(*p*-aminophenylsulphones) has been just published by Cutter, Danielson and Golden (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1051), the preparation and the properties of the compounds that have been so far studied in this laboratory are being recorded in the body of this paper (*cf.* Sikdar and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 343).

The sulphones were generally prepared by the action of the sodium salt of *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphinic acid, prepared from the corresponding sulphonyl chlorides on the appropriate haloid compound in alcoholic suspension followed by hydrolysis of the resulting acetamido compound to the free amines. The reactions involved may be illustrated as follows:—

In cases of *p*-aminomethylbenzene sulphone compounds the starting materials were again the *p*-acetamidomethylbenzene sulphonyl chloride, prepared by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on acetylbenzylamine according to a method similar to that of Smiles and Stewart (*cf.* "Organic Synthesis", Vol. V, p. 2).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Sulphinates.—The acetyl derivative of the sulphinic acid was prepared by reducing the corresponding sulphonyl chloride with sodium sulphite in a slightly alkaline solution, filtering and acidifying the filtrate with concentrated sulphuric acid. The acid was then converted into its sodium salt by adding requisite amount of sodium bicarbonate in aqueous suspension. The solution obtained was filtered and concentrated to get the sodium salt used in the following preparations.

Preparation of Acetaminosulphone Derivatives.—Equimolecular proportions of acetamino- or acetaminomethylphenyl sodium sulphinates and the mono-haloid deriva-

tives (e.g., benzyl chloride, chloroacetone and allyl bromide) were dissolved in alcohol (95%) and the mixtures were refluxed for 5 to 6 hours in a boiling water-bath. The reaction mixture was then filtered, and the filtrate on cooling, concentration or evaporation afforded the sulphone derivative. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol.

In case of the ethylene-*bis*-sulphone derivatives one molecule of ethylene dibromide was treated with two molecules of the sodium salt of the sulphinic acid derivative and the final product was crystallised from dilute acetic acid.

Hydrolysis.—In order to obtain the free sulphone the above acetylated product (one part) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% hydrochloric acid (25-30 parts) for about 4 to 6 hours. The hydrolysed solution was generally treated with charcoal, filtered and the filtrate on concentration afforded the sulphone in shining crystals. These sulphones are almost insoluble in water, but readily dissolve in alcohol. The aminomethylphenyl sulphones were isolated in the form of their hydrochlorides, and these are readily soluble in water.

The different compounds prepared, their melting points and analyses are being recorded in the following table.

TABLE I

Compound.	M.p. (uncorr)	Formula.	Analyses			Found S.
			Calculated N.	S.	N.	
4-Acetaminophenyl-benzyl sulphone	180°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ NS	4.84%		4.97%	
4-Aminophenyl-benzyl sulphone	216-17°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	5.66	12.95%	5.73	12.89%
4-Acetaminophenyl-acetyl sulphone	115°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ NS	5.49		5.67	
4-Aminophenyl-acetyl sulphone	135°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₃ NS	6.57	15.02	6.69	15.07
4-Acetaminophenyl-allyl sulphone	98-100°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS	5.85		6.04	
4-Aminophenyl allyl-sulphone	106°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	7.1		7.28	
4-Acetaminomethylphenyl acetyl sulphone	143-44°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ NS	5.21		5.48	
4-Aminomethyl phenyl-acetyl sulphone hydrochloride	208° (decomp.)	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ NSCl	5.31	(Cl) 13.47	5.46	(Cl) 12.77
Ethylene- <i>bis</i> -(4-acetaminophenyl-sulphone)	292°* (decomp.)	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₂ S ₂	6.60		6.75	
Ethylene- <i>bis</i> -(4-aminophenyl sulphone)	336°*** (decomp.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	8.23		8.36	
Ethylene- <i>bis</i> -(4-acetaminomethylphenyl sulphone)	264°	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₆ N ₂ S ₂	6.22		6.11	
Ethylene- <i>bis</i> -(4-aminomethylphenyl sulphone dihydrochloride)	320° (char.)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	6.35	(Cl) 16.1	6.46	(Cl) 16.03

* Cutter *et al* (*loc. cit.*) recorded 284-285° (decomp.);

** " " " " recorded 328-330° (decomp.).

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Dr. U. P. Basu for his interest in this investigation.